

Middle-Level Leadership Style and the Effects of Stress among Nurses in Primary Health Care, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

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Abstract

Introduction: Nursing is an important profession in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, with nurses comprising more than 80% of the individuals providing health care services, which will increase by 2030. Therefore, developing and maintaining effective nursing leadership is critical to achieving organizational goals and maintaining quality of care despite the challenging healthcare environment. **Methods:** The data were collected through the distribution of two tools, the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale, as a tool to evaluate stress, and the Leadership Style Questionnaire, among 204 nurse workforce members and 57 middle-level nurse managers who belong to Prince Sultan Military Medical City, Riyadh City, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The study used a cross-sectional survey design and descriptive correlation analysis. **Results:** The study indicated associations of age, nationality, and years of working experience as demographic characteristics with the level of stress experienced by the participants. No association was found between demographic characteristics and depression. Moreover, the study illustrated that middle-level leaders show different leadership styles. The findings also indicated an association between years of working experience and a democratic leadership style. In conclusion, no single leadership style is appropriate for every leader in every situation. Demographic characteristics such as age, nationality, and years of working experience showed associations with the level of stress experienced by the nurse workforce. However, they had no association with depression. **Conclusion and Recommendation:** Investigating the key reasons for the development of stress and depression in nursing staff is crucial. Accordingly, nurses must have opportunities to voice their complaints and ideas about improving the work environment. Educating nurse managers and head nurses about the different styles of leadership; and, how they should select suitable managerial aspects to fit the situation is also important. Further investigations are indicated to explore what triggers stress and depression among the nursing workforce.

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Introduction

Nursing is an important profession in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. Nurses comprise more than 80% of individuals providing health care services, which will increase by 2030 as different infections emerge [1]. Saudi Arabia has confronted a nursing deficiency and difficulties in the nursing workplace. Nursing has advanced since the advancement of the Vision 2030 program, which adds to critical enhancements in the space of the medical services conveyance framework, nursing, schooling, business, correspondence, innovation, and science. The interest in nursing in Saudi Arabia is estimated to increase twofold in the next decade [1].

Leadership is a fundamental capability of the management of any organization that guides assets to further develop proficiency and accomplish hierarchical objectives. The job of leadership in medical services is substantially more significant because it is connected to patient mortality, the nature of patient consideration and fulfillment, and staff skill and confidence development. Moreover, nursing assumes a key role in the medical services framework in spurring and motivating attendants to practice as well as be expected and give high-quality care to patients [2]. Leadership styles vary from organization to organization and from individual to individual. Various leadership styles are effective in health care to develop strategies and manage the work environment. Half of the clinics that provide more than 70% of health services in Saudi Arabia are staffed by nurses because they are the backbone of the healthcare system [3].

Developing and maintaining viable nursing initiatives is important to accomplish hierarchical objectives and keep up with the nature of care despite a difficult medical services climate. Consultations about how managers lead and the effect of leadership on organizations and work adequacy are not new. In 2004, the Institute of Medicine (US) Board of Trustees on Attendant Workplace and Patient Security recognised the need to carry out groundbreaking research in nurturing administration endeavours to address workplace deficiencies [2]. The American Nurses Credentialing Center endorsed this recommendation in 2017 in its revised Magnet model by identifying transformational leadership as one of five components necessary for an organization to be recognised for excellence in nursing. The importance of effective leadership for organizations and employees is demonstrated in the literature, and its influence has been shown in the health care setting [2].

The transformation and challenges inherent in the healthcare system in Saudi Arabia highlight the importance of ensuring that nurses are effective leaders to meet future organizational needs. Therefore, conducting further qualitative and quantitative

research with this group of nurses is important to provide evidence on how leadership style is perceived and how it may influence outcomes in the nursing workforce and work environment [2]. Therefore, this research aimed to explore average leadership styles and the impact of psychological stress among nurses.

A research gap exists concerning leadership style and its impact on nursing stress. Although many studies have suggested that a transformational leadership style is important in addressing nursing staff issues, studies are lacking on specific leadership traits and techniques that nurse managers can use to enhance their leadership style and improve staff satisfaction.

This research aimed to explore middle-level leadership styles and the effects of stress on nursing. The aim of this study led to these objectives:

- Explore middle-level leadership styles and nursing stress.
- Establish the relationship between the different leadership styles and the effects of stress among nurses.

Study hypotheses are:

- An association exists between the level of stress or depression in nurses and their demographic characteristics.
- An association exists between various leadership styles in middle-level nursing managers and their demographic characteristics.

Saudi Arabia's medical system is expanding rapidly as resources are created to achieve the 2030 Vision of creating a comprehensive, efficient, and comprehensive healthcare system. As the duties in nursing management increase and new nursing jobs are established and implemented to meet the fluctuating difficulties of health care, these changes have presented many problems.

Previous research suggests that limited literature exists on strategies for developing leadership styles in hospitals for nursing staff. Such strategies help them enhance their leadership qualities to resolve nurses' issues and empower them to increase their commitment to their work. This review focuses primarily on the middle-leadership styles and the effects of stress among nurses.

Working Definitions

Leadership: The practice of encouraging others to do their best towards an achievement.

Transformational leadership (relational): This type of leadership is described as a method in which leaders recognize the values of their followers, stimulate new ideas, and motivate and help them, resulting in their positive development and growth.

Authentic leadership: A new leadership method that emerged as an important component of positive organizational psychology and has demonstrated promising results, notably in supporting employee

health and well-being via the creation of positive work environments.

Ethical leadership: Has been shown to stimulate organizational citizenship, commitment, and employee job satisfaction.

Burnout: A response to job-related heavy stress. A sense of mental exhaustion and a shortage of emotional support.

Emotional exhaustion: An unpleasant and isolated reaction to surroundings and loss of idealism.

Depersonalization: A feeling of incompetence or failure to perform perfectly at work, with reduced personal accomplishment.

Literature Review and Framework

Leadership styles impact employee proficiency and productivity, including elements such as creativity, passion, and job satisfaction, which are key factors in motivating employees [4].

The study suggests that transformational leadership is the most suitable type of leadership for Saudi Arabia's healthcare system. Change leaders may be able to influence the nursing profession, bring about positive changes, and resolve conflicts.

[5] reported that leadership style is one of the variables that can worsen the experience of burnout in nurses. Almost half of the research in their systematic review found that certain leadership styles led to increased psychological discomfort, desire to leave the profession, and burnout symptoms in nurses, as well as worse work satisfaction. More than half of the research found that certain leadership styles affected nurse burnout reduction.

Leadership style has an impact on a nurse's behavior at work, either positively or negatively. Employees may encounter psychological stress if they feel their leaders are inefficient, such as in abusive leadership, laissez-faire leadership, exploitative leadership, and despotic leadership.

Four leadership styles impact nurse burnout reduction because they may be more efficient and applicable in the surroundings of healthcare employees, especially nurses and researchers concerned with leadership. Nurse leaders must establish and maintain a healthy work environment to enhance their proficiency and physical and emotional well-being. Nurse leaders who create a healthy workplace provide nurses with organizational support, opportunities, resources, and an enjoyable, collaborative work environment [6].

These leadership styles are transformational leadership, authentic leadership, servant leadership and ethical leadership.

This type of leadership is a method in which leaders recognise the values of their followers, stimulate new ideas, motivate them and help them, resulting in positive development and growth of their followers [7]. Transformational leadership has consistently been

connected to various work outcomes for health care workers, especially nurses, in the clinical setting. These include creative work behaviour, increased nurse satisfaction, decreased burnout, increased psychological interaction, organizational dedication, employee well-being and competency to be committed to the organization. Transformational leadership necessitates a skilled and imaginative leader [5]. Transformational leaders are also known as relationship leaders [8].

Authentic leadership has long been connected principally with patient care and humanitarianism; both principles are necessary to nursing in general. Authentic leadership is a new leadership method that emerged as an important component of positive organizational psychology and has demonstrated promising results, notably in supporting employee health and well-being via the creation of positive work environments [5].

Servant leadership is an emergent leadership style in which leaders direct their focus to the development and personal growth of their followers by trying to serve them ethically. Servant leadership has also been characterised as "enabling and encouraging people who are under the leader's impact instead of using force and position to get a task" [9]. Servant leadership's two components (serve and lead) are significant to organizational progress [10].

Ethical leadership has been shown to stimulate organizational citizenship, commitment, progress and employee job satisfaction. When ethical leadership has a direct effect on positive organizational goals and behaviors, it also has an adverse impact on negative elements such as work stress, job dissatisfaction and burnout. This style of leadership demands leaders that support and encourage their followers. Their principles include trust, responsibility, dependability, fairness, honesty, integrity and motivation, which leads to good evaluations and decreases burnout [5].

Several models have been created using this strategy, which was popular in the 1960s. Fielder's contingency theory, Hershey and Blanchard's situational leadership model, Vroom and Yetton's model, and House and Mitchell's path-goal model are the prominent models. Researchers have noted over the years that leaders typically respond differently in different settings and alter their leadership style based on a range of criteria in the scenarios they experience [11].

Although behavioural leadership theories can help leaders, they do not give enough guidance on what defines good leadership in a range of circumstances [11].

Contingency theories of leadership are those that illustrate leadership efficiency in terms of organizational moderator factors [12]. These ideas highlight the connection between leadership styles and

organizational progress. "Contingency means that one thing depends on other things, and for a leader to be effective there must be suitable fit between the leader's behavior and style and the conditions in the situation" [11].

In the 1980s, scholars grew interested in the emotional and symbolic components of leadership, which resulted in the development of charismatic and transformational leadership theories. These were developed to understand how leaders influence their followers to create self-devotion and prioritise the objective of the company over their own. Leaders are those who empower others by their behaviours, ideas and words [13]. Many writers use the terms transformational and charismatic interchangeably, although some major distinctions exist [12]. Since the 1980s, the transformational theory has been one of the most prominent methods among researchers. It is an integral part of the 'new leadership' paradigm, which promotes charismatic and passionate aspects of leadership in many disciplines such as nursing, education and industrial engineering [14].

Burns classified leadership into two categories: transformational and transactional.

Transformational

a) Transformational leaders motivate their subordinates and stimulate their self-interests for the scope of the organization [11].

b) Transformational leadership exceeds transactional leadership and is preferable because it develops levels of followers' effort and achievements that surpass what transactional leadership can do alone [11].

c) Transformational leaders make followers empowered and energised to do more [11].

d) Leaders permit their staff to become leaders via a healthy connection with them to maintain the organization's goals in accordance with the team's vision [15].

e) An example of this model of leadership is politicians who promise 'no new taxes' or instructors who give awards for work completed [14].

Transactional Leaders

a) According to Ohio State experiments, Fielder's model and path-goal theory, transactional leaders direct their followers toward specified goals by clarifying the job description and requirements [11].

b) Transactional leadership focuses on the transactions that occur between leaders, colleagues and customers. It is based on the leader's communication with others about the need for tasks to be completed, as well as the selection of incentives for motivation and achievement of outcomes [16].

c) The transactional leader identifies the needs of followers and determines how those needs and desires will be met in line with the required tasks [14].

[16] revealed that both transformational and transactional leadership styles have a significant influence on organizational performance when used in complementary ways. However, discriminations present between transactional leadership [16] According to [17], followers show high levels of job satisfaction when working with a transformational leader.

[18] revealed that emotional intelligence (EI) has a positive effect on work performance and the efficiency of leadership styles. Nurses with higher EI have higher proficiency. [18] recommended workshops and training programmes in the areas of concern to enhance awareness of nurse leaders' responsibility and leadership styles.

[19] recommended that the method of applying transformational leadership in a long-term care organization be investigated. The nursing home in that study chose administrators for further training to help them understand how to be a transformational leader, which may impact the organization. Their transformational leadership programme focused on developing connections and trust, motivating staff, incorporating knowledge, leading, supporting change, managing difficulties and balancing responsibilities. When trust was established, empowerment resulted. The staff of freshly trained administrators were supported in taking on new projects and offered opportunities for progress. Frontline employees learned about the organization's culture and expectations while serving as change agents within it. [20] revealed a significant (moderate) relationship between a transformational management style and the outcomes of management as a long way as more attempt ($p = 0.000$), effectiveness ($p = 0.000$) and delight ($p = 0.000$).

[21] concluded that nurse leaders can use a combination of transformational and transactional leadership to improve job satisfaction and nursing service. Transformational and transactional leadership styles can also decrease nurse work stress and intention to leave the profession.

[22] suggested that EI can be used as a psychological tool to resolve the complications brought about by certain leadership styles. [4] found that EI skills and abilities can efficiently reduce psychological stress and burnout in a challenging work atmosphere. They reported that the jobs of nurse managers demand sufficient supplies, an established partition of labour and more competent frameworks. Statistical analysis revealed that nearly every fifth nurse manager encountered a heavy workload, which was correlated with higher overall job stress, a higher desire to leave the organization, job dissatisfaction (both personally and professionally) and a less favourable view of the practice environment.

The conceptual framework encompasses an in-depth comprehension of diverse leadership styles that leaders can adopt within the healthcare context. These styles encompass effective and ineffective leadership styles. These styles are utilized to guide leader conduct and their influence on individuals and organizations. The conceptual framework explores various variables that may impact leadership styles and nursing stress. These variables include demographic characteristics of nurses, such as age, nationality, and work experience, alongside other factors such as the work environment, organizational culture, and job stress. The examination of these variables aims to comprehend the potential relationships and effects among them. The conceptual framework delves into the potential ramifications of leadership styles and stress on nurses, their performance, and job satisfaction. It analyzes how these factors impact the level of stress and fatigue among nurses, as well as their overall performance and job satisfaction. The research endeavors to comprehend the relationships and offer robust evidence to support the impact of leadership and stress on nurses. The conceptual framework identifies a research gap in the existing literature concerning strategies for fostering leadership styles within hospital nursing teams. The identification of this research gap necessitates a review of previous studies and pertinent literature on nursing leadership and its influence on nurses. This research strives to address this gap and provide additional evidence and recommendations for the development of effective leadership strategies in nursing.

Leadership is the practice of encouraging others to do their best towards an achievement. It requires creating and expressing an outlook for the future, motivating others and obtaining their cooperation. Leaders are accountable for the results of the organization and their own credibility [11]. They also guide and set goals for followers to improve organizational objectives [23].

According to behavioural theories, leadership styles can be categorised into two types: task behaviours and relationship behaviours. Task behaviours help in achieving targets by providing structure and defining roles. Relationship behaviours create a comfortable atmosphere for employees and enhance their satisfaction with themselves and their surroundings [14].

Douglas McGregors' book *The Human Side of Enterprise* clarified all behavioural concepts by saying that a person's views on human beings impact their style of leadership and management. Additionally, studies at the University of Michigan and Ohio State, as well as the Black of Mouton Managerial Grid Model of Leadership, were crucial in the creation of behavioural theory in leadership research [11].

Although early leadership theories focused on efficient leaders' qualifications and behaviours, recent theories have begun to highlight the duties of employees and the broader elements of leadership [11]. Before the 1980s, three basic approaches existed to examining leadership: trait, style and contingency. An evolution in leadership theory has occurred since the early 1980s, expanding concepts to include charismatic and transformational leadership. The start of this new phase did not wholly ignore the influence of the previous one; rather, it represented a shift in priority [11].

Researchers have recommended that no single leadership style is suitable for every leader in every case [11]. The following factors can determine leadership style:

- **Situational variables** such as task, structure, atmosphere and context.
- **The nature of followers.** The significance of factors such as maturity, needs and integration into leadership models has been emphasised [11].

Stress and burnout

a- Job stress

Work demands put physical and emotional pressure on nurses, which is detrimental to their health, work happiness and productivity [24]. Job-related stress causes psychological disorders. Nurses have more stress-related problems than other vocations [4]

b- Burnout

[25] described burnout as a state of physical, emotional and psychological strain in nurses as a result of stressful work circumstances that become out of control.

[26] defined the following:

- Burnout: a response to job-related heavy stress, a sense of being mentally exhausted and a shortage of emotional support.
- Emotional exhaustion: an unpleasant and isolated reaction to one's surroundings and a loss of idealism.
- Depersonalisation: feeling incompetent, failure to do perfectly at work and reduced personal accomplishment.

Maslach developed a scale known as the Maslach Burnout Inventory, which is a burnout-measuring instrument widely used by researchers throughout the world.

Maslach demonstrated that burnout is a condition that occurs as a result of an employee's spontaneous unfulfilled expectations concerning the six elements of work:

- 1) Workload: An excessive quantity of requests, resulting in a lack of achievement.
- 2) Control: Employees' lack of control over the assets required to perform their duties.
- 3) Reward: No valuable payoff for the work done.

4) Community: Employees lack a healthy connection with their colleagues and managers, resulting in a reduction in social relationships and more disillusionment.

5) Fairness: Unjust working treatment, such as unequal pay and workload.

6) Values: The sense of being mistreated and stressed to act against ideals.

Maslach indicated that severe tiredness, negativity and job detachment were the three characteristics of burnout. This three-dimensional approach is significant because it situates individual stress within a social framework that encompasses a person's vision of both themselves and others [27].

[28] defined nursing job performance as nurses' capacity to complete work activities, satisfy job standards, offer standard services and achieve institutional objectives. [8] defined job satisfaction as the influence of mentality, thoughts and behaviour of employees regarding work.

Methods

Research Design

The study implemented a cross-sectional survey design and descriptive correlation analysis.

Sample of the Study

The study was conducted at primary health care centres belonging to PSMMC, Riyadh City, Saudi Arabia (n = 11). PSMMC is part of the Medical Services Department of the Ministry of Defence and is considered one of the most advanced centres in the Middle East. The target population included all registered nurses, with a focus on team leaders, charge nurses and head nurses, currently working at PSMMC primary health care centres (n = 400).

Sampling design

A simple random technique was adopted to select the participants, relying on a listing of all eligible persons that was obtained from the hospital administration.

Sample size calculation

We had a convenient non-probability sample of 50% of the target population + 10% for no response rate, so 197 out of 394 health care workers were calculated. Accordingly, we actually ended up with 204 total sample collected. In addition, the middle-level nurse managers were 57 and they were all selected for participation.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria:

- Working for at least one year in the current facility.
- All genders.
- All nationalities.

Exclusion criteria:

- Newly employed.
- Junior nurses.
- Staff who refused to sign an informed consent.

Research Instruments

Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale

The Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS) is a 14-item, self-report 4-point Likert rating scale (with a range of 0–3). It is intended to assess depression and anxiety, including seven items for each subscale. The author supposes that the level of anxiety can reflect the level of the experienced stress, because both stress and anxiety are interrelated. The sum of the 14 items (ranging from 0 to 21) determines the overall score, and the sum of each subscale's seven items determines the score corresponding to the anxiety and depression components. The interpretation of the recorded score for each subscale is as follows: 0–7 = normal, 8–10 = borderline abnormal and 11–21 = abnormal.

Leadership survey questionnaire

A self-administered questionnaire was used in this study. It comprised two main sections:

- Demographic and work-related characteristics of the participants (age, gender, nationality, job title, years of experience in nursing and the current health care facility, highest qualification, history of attending any course in leadership).

- Leadership style questionnaire. This includes 18 items investigating the most and least prevalent dimensions of the leadership style of the participants. It was designed to evaluate three styles of leadership (authoritarian, democratic and laissez-faire). These three categories are reflected by the participant's cumulative score. The scoring system depends on summing up the responses for items 1, 2, 6, 10, 15 and 16 to indicate the authoritarian leadership dimension, while the sum of responses for items 4, 5, 8, 11, 14 and 18 indicates the democratic leadership dimension, and the sum of responses for items 3, 7, 9, 12, 13 and 17 indicates the laissez-faire style [14].

The interpretation of the recorded score is as follows:

If the score is 26–30, the participant is in the very high range.

If the score is 21–25, the participant is in the high range.

If the score is 16–20, the participant is in the moderate range.

If the score is 11–15, the participant is in the low range.

If the score is 6–10, the participant is in the very low range.

Data Collection

The HADS and leadership survey questionnaires were given by hand to the participants by the investigator and gathered on the same day or at most a day later. Confidentiality was assured to participants after explaining the aim of the study to them.

Data Analysis

The data were entered and analysed using SPSS version 28. Suitable statistical techniques were employed for description and inference. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages and bar charts were

performed to illustrate the information reflected in the collected data. Inferential statistics involved the analysis of the relationship between demographics, the psychological state of the participants and their leadership style. The chi-squared test was used to evaluate the association between the determinants and the outcome variables, where the null hypotheses assumed that the test variables were independent and no association existed between them (p-values of <0.05 were considered statistically significant).

Ethical Consideration

Approval of the study proposal was obtained from the Institutional Review Board (E-2172) to conduct the research. A consent form had to be signed by the participant to ensure their voluntary participation in the study. Participants were informed clearly about the purpose of the study. Honesty during the data analysis process and avoiding sharing only positive results were crucial; multiple aspects were important to include in the final paper. The author kept the participants anonymous. Plagiarism was avoided by citing the proper references. The author avoided disclosing any information that may put the participants at risk, and he will share the results of the study with the participants and concerned stakeholders. The participants were thanked for devoting their time to sharing their experiences.

Study Limitations

Nurses voluntarily participated in this study, which was conducted in 11 primary health care centres belonging to Prince Sultan Military Medical City (PSMMC), Riyadh City, Saudi Arabia. The potential to extrapolate from the study’s findings is restricted because the participants were staff members from specific military

health care centres and do not necessarily represent all hospital staff members in the Kingdom, so the results should be interpreted cautiously. The study may be conducted on a larger scale to include civil health care centres from all over Saudi Arabia to give clearer insights about the nursing workforce in different types of hospitals.

Results

The findings of the study are presented in this section.

Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Participants were taken from the registered nurses currently working at primary health care centres belonging to PSMMC, Riyadh City, Saudi Arabia. The study included 261 nurses in total: 204 who completed a HADS questionnaire and 57 middle-level managers who completed the leadership survey questionnaire. Table 1 shows the demographic responses of the study participants who completed the HADS. Two thirds were women. Most (60%) were 20 to 29 years old, 30% were 30 to 39 years old, and only 6% and 4% of the respondents were 40 to 49 years old and 50 years old and above, respectively. Most participants (83%) were Saudi, and only 17% were non-Saudi. Of the participants, 31% had working experience in the range of 1 to less than 5 years, whereas 27% and 26% had less than 1 year and 10 to less than 20 years of working experience, respectively. Participants with 5 to less than 10 years of working experience and 20 years of working experience or more constituted 12% and 4%, respectively. Concerning education, 71% had bachelor’s degrees, 17% were diploma holders, 6.5% were high-diploma holders, 5% were master’s degree holders, and only one participant (approximately 0.5%) was a PhD holder.

Table 1: Demographic Responses of Nurses Who Completed the HADS

Demographic information	Response	Frequency	Proportion
Gender	Female	144	71%
	Male	60	29%
	Total	204	100%
Age	20 to 29 years	123	60%
	30 to 39 years	61	30%
	40 to 49 years	13	6%
	50 years or above	7	4%
	Total	204	100%
Nationality	Saudi	169	83%
	Non-Saudi	35	17%
	Total	204	100%
Experience in nursing	<1 year	55	27%
	1 to <5 years	63	31%
	5 to <10 years	25	12%
	10 to <20 years	52	26%
	20 years or more	9	4%
	Total	204	100%

Demographic information	Response	Frequency	Proportion
Education	Bachelor’s degree	145	71%
	Diploma	35	17%
	High diploma	13	6.5%
	Master’s degree	10	5%
	PhD	1	0.5%
	Total	204	100%

Table 1 shows the demographic responses of the middle-level managers (n = 57). The number of female participants (n = 27; 47.4%) was almost the same as the number of male participants (n = 30; 52.6%). More than half of the participants (56.1%) were 30 to 39 years old, whereas 21.1% and 15.8% were 20 to 29 years old and 40 to 49 years old, respectively. Only four respondents (7%) were aged 50 years or above. Most participants (80.7%) were Saudi, and only 19.3% were non-Saudi. Of the respondents, 36.8% were team leaders, 33.3% were charge nurses, and 15.8% and 14% were CRNs and head

nurses, respectively. More than half of the respondents (63.2%) had working experience in the range of 10 to less than 20 years, whereas 17.5% and 15.8% had 1 to less than 5 years and 20 years or more, respectively. Participants with less than 1 year of working experience constituted only 3.5%. Concerning education, 66.7% had a bachelor’s degree, 19.3% were master’s degree holders, 7% were diploma holders and 7% were high-diploma holders. Additionally, 73.7% of the participants had a history of attending leadership courses, whereas 26.3% did not.

Table 2: Demographic Responses of Middle-Level Managers Who Completed the Leadership Survey Questionnaire

Demographic information	Response	Frequency	Proportion	Cumulative proportion
Gender	Female	27	47.4%	47.4%
	Male	30	52.6%	100%
	Total	57	100%	
Age	20 to 29 years	12	21.1%	21.1%
	30 to 39 years	32	56.1%	77.2%
	40 to 49 years	9	15.8%	93.0%
	50 years or above	4	7.0%	100.0%
	Total	57	100.0%	
Nationality	Non-Saudi	11	19.3%	19.3%
	Saudi	46	80.7%	100.0%
	Total	57	100.0%	
Job title	Charge nurse	19	33.3%	33.3%
	CRN	9	15.8%	49.1%
	Head nurse	8	14.0%	63.2%
	Team leader	21	36.8%	100.0%
	Total	57	100.0%	
Experience in nursing	1 to less than 5 years	10	17.5%	17.5%
	10 to less than 20 years	36	63.2%	80.7%
	20 years or more	9	15.8%	96.5%
	Less than 1 year	2	3.5%	100.0%
	Total	57	100.0%	
Education	Bachelor’s degree	38	66.7%	66.7%
	Diploma	4	7.0%	73.7%
	High diploma	4	7.0%	80.7%
	Master’s degree	11	19.3%	100.0%
	Total	57	100.0%	
History of attending any	No	15	26.3%	26.3%
	Yes	42	73.7%	100.0%

Demographic information	Response	Frequency	Proportion	Cumulative proportion
course in leadership	Total	57	100.0%	

Impact of Demographic Characteristics on the Level of Stress

This section presents the HADS data to show the impact of demographic characteristics (gender, age, nationality, years of experience in nursing, education) on the recorded level of anxiety which reflects the level of stress of the participants (n = 204). The levels of stress are denoted as 1 = normal, 2 = borderline and 3 = abnormal. The frequencies of responses are summarised in Table 3.

Almost half of the respondents (49%) scored normal, and the other half comprised borderline cases (24.5%) and abnormal cases (26.5%). Female participants showed higher stress than men (144 vs 60). The proportions of borderline and abnormal scores for women were higher than those for men (borderline: 25.7% of women vs 21.7% of men; abnormal: 29.2% of women vs 20.0% of men). The proportion of normal scores for women was lower than that for men (45.1% of women vs 58.3% of men).

The age range of 20 to 29 years represented the most participants (n = 123; 60%), followed by 30 to 39 years (n = 61; 30%), 40 to 49 years (n = 13; 6.5%) and 50 years old or above (n = 7; 3.5%). The age groups 20 to 29 years and 30 to 39 years represented 90% of the participants. Moreover, most of the respondents with normal scores (n = 84; 41.2%) were divided equally between these two age groups. However, the age group 20 to 29 years represented the highest number of respondents with abnormal scores (n = 48).

More participants were Saudi than non-Saudi (169 vs 35), and Saudis tended to show higher stress levels than non-Saudis. The proportions of borderline and abnormal scores for Saudis were higher than those for non-Saudis (borderline: 25.4% of Saudis vs 20.0% of non-Saudis; abnormal: 30.2% of Saudis vs 8.6% of non-Saudis). The proportions of normal scores were lower for Saudis than non-Saudis (44.4% of Saudis vs 71.4% of non-Saudis).

Bachelor’s degree holders represented the most responses (n = 145; 71%), followed by diploma holders (n = 35; 17%), high-diploma holders (n = 13; 6.5%), master’s degree holders (n = 10; 5%) and PhD holders (n = 1; 0.5%). Bachelor’s degree holders most commonly scored normal (42.8%), followed by abnormal (30.3%) and borderline anxious (26.9%). Most diploma holders scored normal (65.7%), followed by borderline anxious (20.0%) and abnormal (14.3%).

The study tested for an association between the level of stress (normal, borderline, abnormal) and demographic characteristics (gender, age, nationality, years of experience in nursing, education) using a chi-square test of independence ($\alpha = 0.05$). The null hypothesis was that the level of stress would be independent of the various demographic characteristics, with no association between them. The test results are illustrated in table 3. The p-value recorded 0.209, 0.000***, 0.007**, 0.000***, and 0.08 for the different demographic features: gender, age, nationality, years of nursing experience, and education respectively. Hence, we did not reject the null hypothesis in the cases of testing the association of gender and education with the experienced level of stress, because the p-value was greater than the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$). In other words, we concluded that insufficient data existed to support a relationship between gender, education and stress level. On the contrary, we rejected the null hypothesis in the cases of testing the association of age, nationality, and years of experience in nursing with the experienced level of experience, because the p-value was less than the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$). We concluded that a relationship existed between stress level and the three demographic characteristics: age, nationality, and years of experience.

Table 3: Crosstabulation of Demographic Characteristics and Stress

Demographic information	Response	Frequency of stress level			Total	P value
		1 = normal	2 = borderline	3 = abnormal		
Gender	Female	65	37	42	144	0.209
	% within female	45.1%	25.7%	29.2%	100.0%	
	Male	35	13	12	60	
	% within male	58.3%	21.7%	20.0%	100.0%	
	Total	100	50	54	204	
	% within gender	49.0%	24.5%	26.5%	100.0%	
Age	20 to 29 years	42	33	48	123	0.000***
	% within age range	34.1%	26.8%	39%	100.0%	

	30 to 39 years old	42	15	4	61	
	% within age range	68.9%	24.6%	6.6%	100.0%	
	40 to 49 years old	10	1	2	13	
	% within age range	76.9%	7.7%	15.4%	100.0%	
	50 years old and above	6	1	0	7	
	% within age range	85.7%	14.3%	0.0%	100.0%	
	Total	100	50	54	204	
Nationality	Non-Saudi	25	7	3	35	0.007**
	% within non-Saudi	71.4%	20.0%	8.6%	100.0%	
	Saudi	75	43	51	169	
	% within Saudi	44.4%	25.4%	30.2%	100.0%	
	Total	100	50	54	204	
Years of experience in nursing	1 to less than 5 years	19	17			0.000***
	% within range	30.2%	27.0%			
	10 to less than 20 years	36	11			
	% within range	69.2%	21.2%			
	20 years or more	8	1			
	% within range	88.9%	11.1%			
	5 to less than 10 years	14	5			
	% within range	56.0%	20.0%			
	Less than 1 year	23	16			
	% within range	41.8%	29.1%			
Total	100	50	54			
% within years of experience	49.0%	24.5%	26.5%			
Education	Bachelor's degree	62	39	44	145	0.08
	% within bachelor's degree	42.8%	26.9%	30.3%	100.0%	
	Diploma	23	7	5	35	
	% within diploma	65.7%	20.0%	14.3%	100.0%	
	High diploma	7	2	4	13	
	% within high diploma	53.8%	15.4%	30.8%	100.0%	
	Master's degree	8	1	1	10	
	% within master's degree	80.0%	10.0%	10.0%	100.0%	
	PhD	0	1	0	1	
	% within PhD	0.0%	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%	
	Total	100	50	54	204	
	% within education	49.0%	24.5%	26.5%	100.0%	

Impact of Demographic Characteristics on the Level of Depression

This section presents the HADS data collected to show the impact of demographic characteristics (gender, age, nationality, years of experience in nursing, education) on the recorded level of depression of the participants (n = 204). The levels of depression are denoted as 1 = normal, 2 = borderline and 3 = abnormal. The frequencies of responses are summarised in Table 4.

More than half of the respondents (59.3%) scored normal, and the remainder included borderline (24.5%) and abnormal scores (16.2%). Women had higher depression scores than men (144 vs 60). However, men showed a higher tendency than women to depression.

The proportions of borderline and abnormal scores for men were greater than those for women (borderline: 30.0% of men vs 22.2% of women; abnormal: 16.7% of men vs 16.0% of women). The proportion of normal scores for men was lower than for women (53.3% of men vs 61.8% of women).

The age range of 20 to 29 years represented the most participants (n = 123; 60%), followed by 30 to 39 years (n = 61; 30%), 40 to 49 years (n = 13; 6.5%) and 50 years or above (n = 7; 3.5%). The age groups of 20 to 29 years and 30 to 39 years constituted 90% of the responses, and most of the respondents with normal scores (n = 105; 51.4%) were in these two groups in a ratio of 2:1. The age group of 20 to 29 years represented the highest number of abnormal scores (n = 23).

More participants were Saudi than non-Saudi (169 vs 35), and Saudi nurses showed a higher tendency than non-Saudis to depression. The proportions of borderline and abnormal scores among Saudi participants were higher than those of non-Saudi nurses (borderline: 24.9% of Saudis vs 22.9% of non-Saudis; abnormal: 17.8% of Saudis vs 8.6% of non-Saudis). The proportion of normal scores for Saudis was lower than for non-Saudis (57.4% of Saudis vs 68.6% of non-Saudis).

Bachelor’s degree holders, who constituted most of the participants (71%), most commonly scored normal (57.9%), followed by borderline (24.1%) and abnormal (17.9%). Similarly, diploma holders (n = 35; 17%) mostly scored normal (62.9%), followed by borderline (28.6%) and abnormal (8.6%).

A chi-square test of independence ($\alpha = 0.05$) was used to examine any correlation between the various

demographic factors (gender, age, nationality, years of nursing experience, education) and the level of depression (normal, borderline, abnormal). The null hypothesis was that no correlation would exist between the various demographic factors and the degree of depression. The test results are illustrated in table 4. The p-value recorded 0.456, 0.265, 0.338, 0.38, and 0.331 for the different demographic features: gender, age, nationality, years of nursing experience, and education respectively. Accordingly, we did not reject the null hypothesis for testing the association between all of the items of demographic features and the experienced level of depression, because the p-value was greater than the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$). In other words, we concluded that insufficient data existed to support a relationship between gender, age, nationality, years of nursing experience, education and depression level.

Table 4: Crosstabulation of Demographic Characteristics and Depression

Demographic information	Response	Frequency of depression level			Total	P value
		1 = normal	2 = borderline	3 = abnormal		
Gender	Female	89	32	23	144	0.456
	% within female	61.8%	22.2%	16.0%	100.0%	
	Male	32	18	10	60	
	% within male	53.3%	30.0%	16.7%	100.0%	
	Total	121	50	33	204	
	% within gender	59.3%	24.5%	16.2%	100.0%	
Age	20 to 29 years	70	30	23	123	0.265
	% within age range	56.9%	24.4%	18.7%	100.0%	
	30 to 39 years	35	19	7	61	
	% within age range	57.4%	31.1%	11.5%	100.0%	
	40 to 49 years	11	0	2	13	
	% within age range	84.6%	0.0%	15.4%	100.0%	
	50 years or above	5	1	1	7	
	% within age range	71.4%	14.3%	14.3%	100.0%	
	Total	121	50	33	204	
	% within age range	59.3%	24.5%	16.2%	100.0%	
Nationality	Non-Saudi	24	8	3	35	0.338
	% within non-Saudi	68.6%	22.9%	8.6%	100.0%	
	Saudi	97	42	30	169	
	% within Saudi	57.4%	24.9%	17.8%	100.0%	
	Total	121	50	33	204	
	% within nationality	59.3%	24.5%	16.2%	100.0%	
Experience in nursing	1 to less than 5 years	35	16			0.38
	% within range	55.6%	25.4%			
	10 to less than 20 years	32	12			
	% within range	61.5%	23.1%			
	20 years or more	7	1			
	% within range	77.8%	11.1%			
	5 to less than 10 years	12	11			
	% within range	48.0%	44.0%			
Less than 1 year	35	10				
	% within range	63.6%	18.2%			

	Total	121	50	33		
	% within years of experience	59.3%	24.5%	16.2%		
Education	Bachelor's degree	84	35	26	145	0.331
	% within bachelor's degree	57.9%	24.1%	17.9%	100.0%	
	Diploma	22	10	3	35	
	% within diploma	62.9%	28.6%	8.6%	100.0%	
	High diploma	10	2	1	13	
	% within high diploma	76.9%	15.4%	7.7%	100.0%	
	Master's degree	5	3	2	10	
	% within master's degree	50.0%	30.0%	20.0%	100.0%	
	PhD	0	0	1	1	
	% within PhD	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
	Total	121	50	33	204	
% within education	59.3%	24.5%	16.2%	100.0%		

Impact of Demographic Characteristics on Middle-Level Manager Leadership Style

This section presents the data collected from the leadership style questionnaire to show the impact of the demographic characteristics (gender, age, nationality, job title, years of experience in nursing, education, history of attending any course in leadership) on the style of leadership of the participants who were middle-level managers (n = 57). The three styles of leadership were authoritarian, democratic and laissez-faire.

Authoritarian leadership style

The frequencies of responses towards the authoritarian leadership style are summarised in Table 5. More than half of the responses (n = 30; 52.6%) were from male participants, whereas female responses constituted 47.4% (n = 27). Male nurses tended to favour highly authoritarian (n = 15) and moderately authoritarian (n = 13) leadership styles to the same approximate extent. Female nurses tended to favour a moderately authoritarian leadership style (n = 16; 59.2%).

More than half of the responses (n = 32; 56.1%) were recorded from participants whose ages ranged from 30 to 39 years, with the age ranges of 20 to 29 years and 40 to 49 years representing 21.1% and 15.8%, respectively. Participants aged 30 to 39 years consisted of 46.8% moderately authoritarian leaders, 40.6% highly authoritarian leaders, and 6.2% each very highly authoritarian and low-authoritarian leaders. Similarly, of the participants aged 20 to 29 years, 50% showed a moderately authoritarian leadership style, 41.7% showed a highly authoritarian style and only 8.3% (n = 1) showed a very highly authoritarian leadership style. Participants aged 40 to 49 years showed only moderately authoritarian (n = 5; 55.5%) and highly authoritarian styles (n = 4; 44.5%).

Nearly half of the Saudi middle-level nurse managers (47.8%) showed a moderately authoritarian leadership style, and most of the remainder showed a highly

authoritarian style (43.5%). Additionally, 63.6% of non-Saudi respondents showed a moderately authoritarian leadership style, with a highly authoritarian leadership style represented by 27.3%.

Regarding job title, most respondents were team leaders (n = 21), followed by charge nurses (n = 19), CRNs (n = 9) and head nurses (n = 8). All categories tended to favour a moderately authoritarian leadership style, followed by a highly authoritarian style, except for head nurses, who favoured the opposite.

Most participants (63.2%) had 10 to less than 20 years of experience in nursing. Participants with 10 to less than 20 years of working experience tended to favour a moderately authoritarian leadership style (n = 17), followed by a highly authoritarian leadership style (n = 15). The same was noted for participants in other ranges of working experience.

Bachelor's degree holders tended to favour a moderately authoritarian leadership style (n = 22), followed by a highly authoritarian leadership style (n = 15). The same was noted for participants of other education levels.

Participants who had previously received leadership training showed a tendency to be moderately authoritarian (n = 21), followed by highly authoritarian (n = 17). The same was noted for the participants who had not attended any leadership courses.

A chi-square test of independence ($\alpha = 0.05$) was used to examine whether a relationship existed between the demographic characteristics (gender, age, nationality, job title, years of nursing experience, education, history of attending leadership courses) and leadership styles of middle-level managers (authoritarian, democratic, laissez-faire). The null hypothesis was that no correlation would exist between the leadership style and the various demographic traits and that they would be independent of one another. Table 5 illustrates the results for the authoritarian leadership style, where the p-value recorded 0.453, 0.946, 0.599, 0.812, 0.97,

0.133, and 0.643 for gender, age, nationality, job title, years of nursing experience, education, history of attending leadership courses respectively. All the p-values were insignificant (i.e. >0.05). Therefore, we did

not reject the null hypothesis. We concluded that no associations were found between the various demographic traits and the authoritarian leadership style of the participants.

Table 5: Demographic Characteristics Crosstabulation with Authoritarian Group

Demographic information		Authoritarian Group								Total		P value
		5		4		3		2		Count	%	
		Count	%	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%			
Gender	Female	2	66.7%	8	34.8%	16	55.2%	1	50%	27	47.4%	0.453
	Male	1	33.3%	15	65.2%	13	44.8%	1	50%	30	52.6%	
Age	20 to 29 years old	1	33.3%	5	21.7%	6	20.7%	0	0%	12	21.1%	0.946
	30 to 39 years old	2	66.7%	13	56.5%	15	51.7%	2	100%	32	56.1%	
	40 to 49 years old	0	0%	4	17.4%	5	17.2%	0	0%	9	15.8%	
Nationality	Non-Saudi	1	33.3%	3	13%	7	24.1%	0	0%	11	19.3%	0.599
	Saudi	2	66.7%	20	87%	22	75.9%	2	100%	46	80.7%	
Job title	Charge nurse	1	33.3%	9	39.1%	9	31%	0	0%	19	33.3%	0.812
	CRN	1	33.3%	3	13%	5	17.2%	0	0%	9	15.8%	
	Head nurse	0	0%	4	17.4%	3	10.3%	1	50%	8	14%	
	Team Leaders	1	33.3%	7	30.4%	12	41.4%	1	50%	21	36.8%	
Years of experience in nursing	1 to Less than 5 years	1	33.3%	3	13%	6	20.7%	0	0%	10	17.5%	0.97
	10 to Less than 20 years	2	66.7%	15	65.2%	17	58.6%	2	100%	36	63.2%	
	20 years or more	0	0%	4	17.4%	5	17.2%	0	0%	9	15.8%	
Education	Bachelor Degree	1	33.3%	15	65.2%	22	75.9%	0	0%	38	66.7%	0.133
	Diploma	0	0%	2	8.7%	1	3.4%	1	50%	4	7%	
	High diploma	0	0%	2	8.7%	2	6.9%	0	0%	4	7%	
	Master Degree	2	66.7%	4	17.4%	4	13.8%	1	50%	11	19.3%	
History of attending any course in leadership	No	0	0%	6	26.1%	8	27.6%	1	50%	15	26.3%	0.643
	Yes	3	100%	17	73.9%	21	72.4%	1	50%	42	73.7%	

Note: 5 = very highly authoritarian, 4 = highly authoritarian, 3 = moderately authoritarian, 2 = low authoritarian

Democratic leadership style

The frequencies of responses towards the democratic leadership style are summarised in Table 6. Male nurses tended to favour a very highly democratic leadership style (n = 14; 46.6%), whereas female nurses tended to favour a highly democratic leadership style (n = 17; 63%). Participants aged 30 to 39 years old consisted of 50% very highly democratic, 40.6% highly democratic and 9.4% moderately democratic leaders. Among participants aged 20 to 29 years, 66.6% showed a highly democratic leadership style, and 16.7% each showed a very highly and moderately democratic leadership style. Participants aged 40 to 49 years showed a highly

democratic (n = 6; 66.7%), very highly democratic (n = 2; 22.2%) or moderately democratic style (n = 1; 11.1%). More than half of Saudi middle-level nurse managers (52.2%) showed a highly democratic leadership style, with 39.1% showing a very highly democratic style and only 8.7% showing a moderately democratic style. Of non-Saudi respondents, 54.5% showed a highly democratic leadership style, whereas a very highly democratic style was represented by 27.3%. Regarding job title, team leaders were most common (n = 21), followed by charge nurses (n = 19), CRNs (n = 9) and head nurses (n = 8). All categories most commonly favoured a highly democratic leadership style, followed

by a very highly democratic style, except for charge nurses, who favoured the opposite.

Participants with 10 to less than 20 years of working experience most commonly favoured a very highly democratic leadership style (n = 18), followed by a highly democratic style (n = 15). In contrast, participants with other ranges of working experience tended to favour a highly democratic leadership style, followed by a very highly democratic style.

Bachelor’s degree holders tended to favour a highly democratic leadership style (n = 22), followed by a very highly democratic style (n = 13). Participants who had previously received leadership training showed a tendency to be highly democratic (n = 21), followed by very highly democratic (n = 17). The same was noted for the participants who did not attend any leadership courses.

A chi-square test of independence ($\alpha = 0.05$) was used to examine whether a relationship existed between the demographic characteristics (gender, age, nationality, job title, years of nursing experience, education, history of attending leadership courses) and leadership styles

of middle-level managers (authoritarian, democratic, laissez-faire). The null hypothesis was that no correlation would exist between the leadership style and the various demographic traits and that they would be independent of one another. Table 6 represents the results for the democratic leadership style. The p-values were greater than the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) (0.257, 0.376, 0.575, 0.328, 0.228, and 0.627) in the cases of all the demographic features: gender, age, nationality, job title, education, and history of attending leadership courses respectively except for years of nursing experience, where the p-value recorded 0.03* (i.e. < 0.05). Accordingly, we rejected the null hypothesis and concluded that an association existed between the years of experience in nursing and the democratic leadership style of the participants. Moreover, we accepted the null hypothesis relevant to the other demographic traits and concluded that insufficient evidence suggested an association between gender, age, nationality, job title, education, history of attending leadership courses and democratic leadership style of the participants.

Table 6: Demographic Characteristics Crosstabulation with Democratic Group

Demographic information		Democratic Group						Total		P value
		5		4		3				
		Count	%	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%	
Gender	Female	7	33.3%	17	56.7%	3	50%	27	47.4%	0.257
	Male	14	66.7%	13	43.3%	3	50%	30	52.6%	
Age	20 to 29 years old	2	9.5%	8	26.7%	2	33.3%	12	21.1%	0.376
	30 to 39 years old	16	76.2%	13	43.3%	3	50%	32	56.1%	
	40 to 49 years old	2	9.5%	6	20%	1	16.7%	9	15.8%	
Nationality Job title	Non-Saudi	3	14.3%	6	20%	2	33.3%	11	19.3%	0.575
	Saudi	18	85.7%	24	80%	4	66.7%	46	80.7%	
	Charge nurse	10	47.6%	8	26.7%	1	16.7%	19	33.3%	0.328
	CRN	4	19%	5	16.7%	0	0%	9	15.8%	
	Head nurse	3	14.3%	4	13.3%	1	16.7%	8	14%	
Team leader	4	19%	13	43.3%	4	66.7%	21	36.8%		
Experience in nursing	1 to less than 5 years	0	0%	9	30%	1	16.7%	10	17.5%	0.03*
	10 to less than 20 years	18	85.7%	15	50%	3	50%	36	63.2%	
	20 years or more	2	9.5%	6	20%	1	16.7%	9	15.8%	
Education	Bachelor’s degree	13	61.9%	22	73.3%	3	50%	38	66.7%	0.228
	Diploma	1	4.8%	1	3.3%	2	33.3%	4	7%	
	High diploma	2	9.5%	2	6.7%	0	0%	4	7%	
	Master’s degree	5	23.8%	5	16.7%	1	16.7%	11	19.3%	
History of attending any	No	4	19%	9	30%	2	33.3%	15	26.3%	0.627
	Yes	17	81%	21	70%	4	66.7%	42	73.7%	

course in leadership													
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Note: 5 = very highly democratic, 4 = highly democratic, 3 = moderately democratic

Laissez-faire leadership style

The frequencies of responses towards the laissez-faire leadership style are summarised in Table 7. Male nurses tended to similarly favour highly (n = 10), moderately (n = 9) and low laissez-faire (n = 9) leadership styles, whereas female nurses tended to favour a moderately laissez-faire style (n = 18; 66.6%).

Participants aged 30 to 39 years old consisted of 40.6% moderately laissez-faire, 31.2% highly laissez-faire and 25% low laissez-faire leaders. Similarly, of participants aged 20 to 29 years, 58.3% showed a moderately laissez-faire leadership style, 25% showed a highly laissez-faire style and 16.6% showed a low laissez-faire style. Participants aged 40 to 49 years old mainly showed a moderately laissez-faire leadership style (n = 6; 66.6%).

Nearly half of Saudi middle-level nurse managers (45.6%) showed moderate laissez-faire leadership style, whereas 28.2% and 27.7% showed highly and low laissez-faire styles, respectively. Of non-Saudi respondents, 54.5% showed a moderately laissez-faire leadership style, whereas a highly laissez-faire style was represented by 27.3%.

Nurse leaders with all job titles tended to favour a moderately laissez-faire leadership style, followed by a highly laissez-faire style, except for head nurses, who most commonly favoured a highly laissez-faire style. Participants with 10 to less than 20 years of working experience tended to favour a moderately laissez-faire leadership style (n = 15), followed by a highly laissez-

faire style (n = 11). The same was noted for participants with other ranges of working experience.

Bachelor’s degree holders tended to favour a moderately laissez-faire leadership style (n = 19), followed by a highly laissez-faire leadership style (n = 10). The same was noted for participants of other education levels. Participants who had previously received leadership training showed a tendency to be moderately laissez-faire (n = 19), followed by highly laissez-faire (n = 12). The same was noted for the participants who did not attend any leadership courses. A chi-square test of independence ($\alpha = 0.05$) was used to examine whether a relationship existed between the demographic characteristics (gender, age, nationality, job title, years of nursing experience, education, history of attending leadership courses) and leadership styles of middle-level managers (authoritarian, democratic, laissez-faire). The null hypothesis was that no correlation would exist between the leadership style and the various demographic traits and that they would be independent of one another. Table 7 illustrates the results for the laissez-faire leadership style, where the p-value recorded 0.065, 0.579, 0.953, 0.127, 0.637, 0.492, and 0.926 for gender, age, nationality, job title, years of nursing experience, education, history of attending leadership courses respectively. All the p-values were insignificant (i.e. >0.05). Therefore, we accepted the null hypothesis and concluded that no associations were found between the various demographic traits and the laissez-faire leadership style of the participants.

Table 7: Demographic Characteristics Crosstabulation with Laissez-Faire Group

Demographic information		Laissez-faire Group										Total		P value
		5		4		3		2		1		Cou nt	%	
		Cou nt	%	Cou nt	%	Cou nt	%	Cou nt	%	Cou nt	%			
Gender	Female	0	0%	6	37.5%	18	66.7%	3	25%	0	0%	27	47.4%	0.065
	Male	1	100%	10	62.5%	9	33.3%	9	75%	1	100%	30	52.6%	
Age	20 to 29 years	0	0%	3	18.8%	7	25.9%	2	16.7%	0	0%	12	21.1%	0.579
	30 to 39 years	0	0%	10	62.5%	13	48.1%	8	66.7%	1	100%	32	56.1%	
	40 to 49 years	1	100%	1	6.3%	6	22.2%	1	8.3%	0	0%	9	15.8%	
Nationality	Non-Saudi	0	0%	3	18.8%	6	22.2%	2	16.7%	0	0%	11	19.3%	0.953
	Saudi	1	100%	13	81.3%	21	77.8%	10	83.3%	1	100%	46	80.7%	
Job title	Charge nurse	0	0%	6	37.5%	8	29.6%	5	41.7%	0	0%	19	33.3%	0.127

	CRN	0	0%	2	12.5%	5	18.5%	1	8.3%	1	100%	9	15.8%	
	Head nurse	1	100%	4	25%	1	3.7%	2	16.7%	0	0%	8	14%	
Experience in nursing	1 to less than 5 years	0	0%	2	12.5%	6	22.2%	2	16.7%	0	0%	10	17.5%	0.637
	10 to less than 20 years	0	0%	11	68.8%	15	55.6%	9	75%	1	100%	36	63.2%	
	20 years or more	1	100%	3	18.8%	4	14.8%	1	8.3%	0	0%	9	15.8%	
Education	Bachelor's degree	0	0%	10	62.5%	19	70.4%	8	66.7%	1	100%	38	66.7%	0.492
	Diploma	0	0%	0	0%	3	11.1%	1	8.3%	0	0%	4	7%	
	High diploma	0	0%	1	6.3%	3	11.1%	0	0%	0	0%	4	7%	
History of attending any course in leadership	No	0	0%	4	25%	8	29.6%	3	25%	0	0%	15	26.3%	0.926
	Yes	1	100%	12	75%	19	70.4%	9	75%	1	100%	42	73.7%	

Note: 5 = very highly laissez-faire, 4 = highly laissez-faire, 3 = moderately laissez-faire, 2 = low laissez-faire, 1 = very low laissez-faire

Summary of findings, conclusion and recommendations

Summary of Findings and Discussion

This study aimed to explore middle-level leadership style and the effects of stress among nurses. The most frequent age of the participants was 20 to 29 years, and most of this age group were women. Most of the respondents aged 30 to 39 years were men. Both nurse and leader participants most commonly had bachelor's degrees and were Saudi.

The study findings indicated an association of age, nationality and years of working experience as demographic characteristics with the level of stress experienced by the participants. The level of stress decreased as age increased. Saudi nurses were more susceptible than non-Saudis to stress, and as years of work experience increased, the level of stress decreased. In contrast, no evidence suggested any association between the demographic characteristics of the participants and their level of depression experienced.

Researchers have indicated that no single leadership style is appropriate for every leader in every situation [11]. The findings of this study are supported by the literature. The study illustrated that middle-level leaders showed various leadership styles. Regarding the exploration of the three categories of leadership among middle-level nurse managers, most of the participants presented their tendency to be moderately authoritarian leaders. Many showed a tendency to be

highly democratic and moderately laissez-faire. This study thus aligns with the literature findings regarding the need for a leader to determine the most suitable leadership style to manage a situation effectively [11].

The study tested for an association between various demographic characteristics and styles of leadership (authoritarian, democratic, laissez-faire). The findings indicated an association between years of working experience and democratic leadership style. Participants who had working experience of 10 to less than 20 years showed a tendency to be very highly democratic. Participants who had working experience of 20 years or more indicated a tendency to be highly democratic. The tendency of middle-level nurse managers to act democratically thus increased as their work experience increased.

Conclusion

The study aimed to explore the middle-level leadership style of nurse managers and the effects of stress among nursing workforces. The findings indicated that no single leadership style is suitable for middle-level nurse managers. It is about fitting the leadership style with the situation ahead. Thus, every leader can present different modes of leadership to cope with the relevant circumstances. Nurse managers can be authoritarian in one situation and democratic in another. The study also showed the limited effect of demographic characteristics on the psychological state of the nursing workforce. Only age, nationality and years of working experience showed associations with the level of stress

experienced by the participants. However, no association was indicated between any demographic characteristic and the level of depression. Accordingly, further investigations are needed concerning what increases the stress and depression levels experienced by nursing workforces.

Recommendations

Multiple recommendations arise from the results of the current study. Investigating the key reasons for the development of stress and depression in nursing staff is crucial. Accordingly, nurses must have opportunities to voice their complaints and ideas about improving the work environment. Such ideas can play a major role in updating managerial policies or targeting relevant workshops and training programs to help raise the morale of nursing staff. Educating nurse managers and head nurses about the different styles of leadership and how they should select suitable managerial aspects to fit the situation is also important. Moreover, the concepts of transformational leadership and emotional intelligence (EI) should be used on a greater scale to enhance work environments and professionalism, which will increase the efficiency of patient care.

References

- [1] Alzailai N, Barriball L, Xyrichis A. Burnout and job satisfaction among critical care nurses in Saudi Arabia and their contributing factors: A scoping review. *Nurs Open*. 2021 Sep;8(5):2331-2344. doi: 10.1002/nop2.843
- [2] Harb A, et al. 'Nurses perceptions of nursing leadership styles in the Eastern Healthcare Cluster in Saudi Arabia. *American Journal of Nursing*, 2022;10(1):13–22. doi: 10.12691/ajnr-10-1-3
- [3] Al-Dossary RN. The Saudi Arabian 2030 vision and the nursing profession: the way forward. *Int Nurs Rev*. 2018 Dec;65(4):484-490. doi: 10.1111/inr.12458
- [4] Alam F, Yang Q, Rüteliöné A, Bhutto MY. Virtual Leadership and Nurses' Psychological Stress during COVID-19 in the Tertiary Hospitals of Pakistan: The Role of Emotional Intelligence. *Healthcare (Basel)*. 2023 May 25;11(11):1537. doi: 10.3390/healthcare11111537
- [5] Roshida DS, Paskarini I, Martiana T. 'Leadership style influence on nurses' burnout: A systematic review', *The Indonesian Journal of Public Health*, 2023;18(3). doi: 10.20473/ijph.v18i2.2023.341-352
- [6] Boamah SA. The impact of transformational leadership on nurse faculty satisfaction and burnout during the COVID-19 pandemic: A moderated mediated analysis. *J Adv Nurs*. 2022 Sep;78(9):2815-2826. doi: 10.1111/jan.15198
- [7] Khan H, et al. Impact of transformational leadership on work performance, burnout and social loafing: A mediation model. *Future Business Journal*, 2020;6:1–13. doi: 10.1186/s43093-020-00043-8
- [8] Hussain M, et al. Impact of leadership styles on work related stress among nurses', *Saudi Journal of Medical and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2017:907–916.
- [9] Amin H, Ahmed F, Soomro RH. Servant leadership improves the knowledge sharing behaviour of employees in organization: A case of higher education sector in Pakistan. *Etikonomi*, 2019;18(1):83–92. doi: 10.15408/etk.v18i1.6190
- [10] Saleem F, et al. Impact of servant leadership on performance: The mediating role of affective and cognitive trust. *Sage Open*, 2020;10(1):2158244019900562. doi: 10.1177/2158244019900562
- [11] Baysak B, Yener Mİ. The relationship between perceived leadership style and perceived stress on hospital employees. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 2015;207:79–89. doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.10.159
- [12] Eze HC. Leadership in organization. *Journal of Nigerian Institute of Management*, 2010;46(1):29–35.
- [13] Robbins SP, Judge TA. *Organizational behavior* 15th edition global edition. England: Pearson Education [Preprint]; 2013.
- [14] Northouse PG. *Leadership: Theory and practice*. Sage Publications; 2021.
- [15] Rolfe P. Transformational leadership theory: What every leader needs to know. *Nurse Leader*, 2011;9(2):54–57. doi: 10.1016/j.mnl.2011.01.014
- [16] Peerman C. The Relationship Between Leadership Styles, Job Satisfaction, and Tenure Among Nursing Home Administrators. *Innov Aging*. 2021 Dec 17;5(Suppl 1):372–3. doi: 10.1093/geroni/igab046.1445
- [17] Alshahrani FM, Baig LA. Effect of Leadership Styles on Job Satisfaction Among Critical Care Nurses in Aseer, Saudi Arabia. *J Coll Physicians Surg Pak*. 2016 May;26(5):366-70.
- [18] Hassan Helaly S, et al. Effects of head nurses' leadership behaviors and social intelligence on staff nurses' job involvement. *Egyptian Journal of Health Care*, 2022;13(4):1308–1322. doi: 10.21608/ejhc.2022.269545
- [19] Karimi B, et al. Transformational leadership at point of care: Approaches and outcomes in a long-term care setting. *Canadian Nursing Home*, 2017;28(1):4–7.
- [20] Albagawi B. Leadership pattern of nurse managers and staff nurses' job satisfaction among government hospitals in Hail city; 2019.
- [21] Pishgooie AH, Atashzadeh-Shoorideh F, Falcó-Pegueroles A, Lotfi Z. Correlation between nursing managers' leadership styles and nurses' job stress and anticipated turnover. *J Nurs Manag*. 2019 Apr;27(3):527-534. doi: 10.1111/jonm.12707
- [22] Mansel B, Einion A. 'It's the relationship you develop with them': emotional intelligence in nurse leadership. A qualitative study. *Br J Nurs*. 2019 Nov

- 28;28(21):1400-1408. doi:
10.12968/bjon.2019.28.21.1400
- [23] Zaman S, et al. Impact of critical success factors and supportive leadership on sustainable success of renewable energy projects: Empirical evidence from Pakistan. *Energy Policy*, 2022;162:112793. doi: 10.1016/j.enpol.2022.112793
- [24] Liu Y, Aunguroch Y, Gunawan J, Zeng D. Job Stress, Psychological Capital, Perceived Social Support, and Occupational Burnout Among Hospital Nurses. *J Nurs Scholarsh*. 2021 Jul;53(4):511-518. doi: 10.1111/jnu.12642
- [25] Gonçalves JV, Castro L, Rêgo G, Nunes R.

- Burnout Determinants among Nurses Working in Palliative Care during the Coronavirus Disease 2019 Pandemic. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2021 Mar 24;18(7):3358. doi: 10.3390/ijerph18073358
- [26] Maslach C, Leiter MP. Understanding the burnout experience: recent research and its implications for psychiatry. *World Psychiatry*. 2016 Jun;15(2):103-11. doi: 10.1002/wps.20311
- [27] Kelly RJ, Hearld LR. Burnout and Leadership Style in Behavioral Health Care: a Literature Review. *J Behav Health Serv Res*. 2020 Oct;47(4):581-600. doi: 10.1007/s11414-019-09679-z

